

EDITORIAL

OPEN ACCESS

Implications of Climate Change on Virulence of Microorganisms

Randeep Singh

Department of Zoology, Khalsa College Amritsar, Punjab, India -143002

Correspondence for materials should be addressed to RS (email: singhrandeep83@hotmail.com)

Received:

2024/07/01

Accepted:

2024/08/18

Published:

2024/09/10

Abstract

Climate change is one of the most serious challenges of the 21st century, with significant impacts on ecosystems, human health, and the global economy. The effect of climate change on flora and fauna has been widely discussed for years. In addition, however, its consequences on microorganisms are generally poorly considered. Climate change is affecting microbial behavior and pathogenicity (Harvell et al., 2002). These microorganisms including bacteria, viruses, fungi, and parasites, play important roles in the environment with significant impacts on human health. Understanding of how climate change can affect their pathogenicity is important to predict and mitigate potential public health risks.

Keywords: Climate; Change; Micro-organisms; Virulence; Microbes; Pathogenicity**Changing Environmental Conditions**

One way by which climate change affects microbes is through changes in environmental conditions viz. increased temperatures, changes in precipitation, and changes in nutrient availability, etc which can directly affect microbial populations (Altizer et al., 2013; Kumar, 2022). For example, warmer temperatures may increase the proliferation of certain microorganisms, leading to changes in microbial community structure. This can affect the prevalence and virulence of pathogenic strains.

Altered Disease Patterns

Climate change is also associated with changes in the spatial distribution of infectious diseases. As temperatures rise, previously temperate regions may become more hospitable to certain microorganisms, allowing them to thrive and potentially lead to outbreaks elsewhere. For example, mosquito-borne disease outbreaks such as Zika and dengue fever are linked to changing climates, empowering mosquitoes to expand their range (McMichael et al., 2006).

Enhanced Adaptation and Evolution

Microbes are incredibly adaptable and can adapt rapidly to changing environments. Higher temperatures, higher CO₂ concentrations, and the presence of variable nutrients create selective pressures that can produce more virulent bacteria (Patz et al., 2005). This phenomenon has been observed in a variety of pathogens, including drug-resistant bacteria and viruses including bacterial transformation.

Impacts on Waterborne Pathogens and Foodborne Diseases

Climate change can also influence the prevalence and virulence of waterborne pathogens. Rising temperatures can lead to warmer water temperatures, creating favorable conditions for the growth of certain bacteria, such as *Vibrio* species, responsible for illnesses like cholera. Changes in precipitation patterns can alter water flow and quality and have affected the distribution of waterborne pathogens (Vezzulli et al., 2016). Likewise, more than 200 types of foodborne diseases have been reported, most of which could be affected by climate change. Approximately 420,000 deaths per year are caused by foodborne diseases which is further expected to increase due to rising temperatures which favor food contamination and pathogen establishment in new temperate regions. The more humid the environment, the greater the survival of pathogens (such as *Trichinella spp.* and *Toxoplasma gondii*) and parasite eggs, larvae, and cysts. The rainfall as well as the increase in floods, favor food contamination because the air bacterial concentration is increased after a drizzle.

Implications for Agriculture and Forest Ecosystems

Microorganisms play important roles in agricultural systems, affecting soil health, nutrient cycling, and plant-bacterial interactions. Climate-induced changes in microbial communities can have significant and long-lasting effects on agricultural production. In addition, changes in temperature and moisture can affect the spread of plant pathogens, potentially increasing yield losses (Anderson et al., 2004). Climate change effects on yields are being analyzed through several models, which predict multi-million-dollar losses to numerous crops throughout the world as a result of pest and pathogen movement to new geographic locations. Similarly, the forest industry accounted for approximately USD 244 billion in derivatives such as paper and paperboard, agglomerates, or pellets in 2020 (<https://www.fao.org/forestry/statistics/80938/en/>, accessed on 19 July 2023). Global warming is affecting the microbial communities of forest soils where a variation of just 5 °C can unbalance the relative abundance of soil microbiota.

Adaptation and Mitigation Strategies

Addressing the implications of climate change on microorganism virulence requires a multi-faceted approach. This includes establishing robust surveillance systems to track changes in microbial populations and disease patterns (Jones et al., 2008), investing in research to understand the mechanisms underlying the impact of climate change on microorganisms, and developing strategies to mitigate adverse effects (Sala et al., 2000), strengthening public health infrastructure to respond effectively to emerging infectious diseases, including those influenced by climate change (Gayer and Heymann, 2009), protecting and restoring ecosystems can help maintain biodiversity, which in turn supports more stable microbial communities and implementing policies to reduce greenhouse gas emissions can help slow down the rate of climate change, providing more time to adapt to its impacts.

Conclusion

Climate change is a complex and multi-faceted challenge that extends beyond absolute warming. The impact on microbial virulence adds another layer of complexity to this global issue. Understanding and addressing these impacts is essential to creating public health and environmental stability in a changing world.

References

- Altizer S, et al. (2013) Climate change and infectious diseases: From evidence to a predictive framework. *Science* 341(6145): 514-519.
- Anderson PK, et al. (2004) Emerging infectious diseases of plants: Pathogen pollution, climate change and agrotechnology drivers. *Trends in Ecology and Evolution* 19(10): 535-544.
- Gayer M and Heymann DL (2009) Control of communicable diseases manual. American Public Health Association.
- Harvell CD, et al. (2002) Climate warming and disease risks for terrestrial and marine biota. *Science* 296(5576): 2158-2162.
- Jones KE, et al. (2008) Global trends in emerging infectious diseases. *Nature* 451(7181): 990-993.
- Kumar R (2022) Climate Change and Resource Conservation: Approaches to Sustainable Agriculture. *Environ Sci Arch* 1(STI-1): 1-2.
- McMichael AJ, et al. (2006) Climate change and the health of nations: Familiar challenges and new responsibilities. *Journal of Epidemiology and Community Health* 60(8): 647-652.
- Patz JA, et al. (2005) Impact of regional climate change on human health. *Nature* 438(7066): 310-317.
- Sala OE, et al. (2000) Global biodiversity scenarios for the year 2100. *Science* 287(5459): 1770-1774.
- Sardana M, Priyadarshi A and Pandit DN (2022) Implications of Climatic Change on Physicochemical Parameters of Freshwater and Fisheries: A Review. *Environ Sci Arch* 1(1):15-22. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7133104
- Vezzulli L, et al. (2016). Climate influence on *Vibrio* and associated human diseases during the past half-century in the coastal North Atlantic. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 113(34): E5062-E5071.

Author Contributions

RS conceived the concept, wrote and approved the manuscript.

Acknowledgements

Not applicable.

Funding

Not applicable.

Availability of data and materials

Not applicable.

Competing interest

The author declares no competing interests.

Ethics approval

Not applicable.

Open Access *This article is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, which permits use, sharing, adaptation, distribution, and reproduction in any medium or format, as long as you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if changes were made. The images or other third-party material in this article are included in the article's Creative Commons license unless indicated otherwise in a credit line to the material. If material is not included in the article's Creative Commons license and your intended use is not permitted by statutory regulation or exceeds the permitted use, you will need to obtain permission directly from the copyright holder. Visit for more details <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.*

Citation: Singh R (2024) Implications of Climate Change on Virulence of Microorganisms. *Environmental Science Archives* 3(2): 51-53.